

Use of Mobile Applications for Learning Academic English among the Undergraduates in Bangladesh

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Abstract: Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) has significantly impacted language learning, offering benefits and challenges. Smartphones provide accessibility, allowing learners to practice anytime and anywhere. Apps and social platforms in smartphones offer adaptive learning paths, allowing learners to focus on vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. The study aimed to assess the impact of mobile applications on learners' English vocabulary, grammar, and writing skills development. A questionnaire survey was conducted among 70 participants from seven Dhaka-based colleges to understand their perception of the impact of MALL. Besides, the researchers adopted pre-test and post-test technique to gather practical data from the students. The data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. The findings show that using a smartphone is thought to be very beneficial for fostering critical thinking skills and teacher-student interaction; the trimmed mean and median values are relatively high, indicating consistent replies by the participants. On the other hand, sectors such as pair activities and group activities exhibit somewhat lower mean scores, indicating room for development in smartphone-based collaborative engagement in Bangladesh context. The researchers argue that MALL is a powerful supplement to traditional language learning, but should be used alongside other methods.

Keywords: Mobile application, academic English, grammar, vocabulary, impact

Introduction

Smartphone is the common term for modern mobile phones nowadays. A mobile phone used to be a cell phone or button phone that exclusively handled voice calls. However, because it has multiple uses, it now looks like a smart one necessary for our day-to-day life. Smartphones facilitate quick and simple communication and at the same time ensure other multifaceted operations (Burston, 2014a). Mobile phones are utilized in education as learning tools in addition to being a source of communication, entertainment, and the necessary arrangements of financial activities (Çakmak, 2019). Due of its ease of use and portability, the device has gained widespread acceptance across learning communities (Böhm & Constantine, 2016). Based on their cognitive state, students can use this gadget to manage their learning process and advance in their own environment (Jeong, 2022). For a number of reasons, the students are drawn to mobile technology. For instance, smartphones have developed into effective language-learning tools due to their adaptability, accessibility, and interactive features (Kim, 2012). The utilization of mobile devices for language acquisition has transformed learners' methods of engaging with a new language. Mobile learning (m-learning) provides numerous advantages by utilizing the effortlessness, accessibility, and interaction of mobile technology to improve the language acquisition process (Burston, 2014b). In response to the

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proliferation of diverse mobile devices, Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) has evolved over the past decade into a distinct and advanced discipline. Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) denotes the utilization of mobile devices, including smartphones, tablets, and other portable gadgets, to enhance the acquisition of a new language (Gafni et al., 2017).

Students can work on developing their language skills whenever and wherever they want because MALL allows them to study a new language without the need for a computer or a desk in a classroom (He & Li, 2023). To sum up, MALL is a great way for language learners to practice in a fun, interactive, and convenient setting. MALL makes language learning more accessible to people all around the world by focusing on customization, real-world communication, and flexibility (Burston, 2014b). One of the most important advantages of using a mobile phone to learn a new language is the abundance of language learning Apps available for smartphones. A growing number of people are turning to mobile Apps as a handy and popular way to learn a new language (Kim, 2012). To keep students interested and involved, many language learning Apps incorporate games, quizzes, and other forms of interactive content. Learning is reinforced and interest is maintained over time through this interaction. Personalized learning routes are made possible by mobile apps that use algorithms to adjust content based on the learner's skill level (Jeong, 2022). Research shows that people learn languages at different rates, and adaptive learning is a great way to meet each student where they are at (Burston, 2014a). As an example, one gamified language learning App is Duolingo, which makes learning a new language more enjoyable and interactive (Berns et al., 2015). It caters to the four language skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing in more than 30 languages. Babel is another App for mobile devices that provides language courses with a structure that mimics natural speech (Chen et al., 2019). Grammar, sentence structure, vocabulary, and speaking practice are the main focuses of this App (Böhm & Constantine, 2016). Anki and Memrise are two examples of Apps developed to aid learning new words by the use of spaced repetition, mnemonic techniques, and flashcards, all of which contribute to better long-term remembering (Chen et al., 2019). Even in English as Foreign Language (EFL) settings, MALL has shown to be an excellent tool for language acquisition (Berns et al., 2015). But there are a variety of new Apps cropping up all the time to help in learning English. Mobile phone users are also becoming more knowledgeable about the language-learning apps available for their cellphones. As a result, the only way for researchers and academics to stay abreast of developments in this area and investigate the potential of smartphones for language acquisition is through systematic research. The researchers in this study took note of the facts and proceeded to examine the effects of mobile applications on undergraduates' acquisition of basic academic English skills in Bangladesh context.

This study aimed to explore how undergraduate students perceive the use of mobile phones for learning academic English and to examine the impact of mobile phone usage on their acquisition of specific language items from the Fundamental English Course.

Literature Review

Mobile has become a significant tool for language learning, contributing greatly to the acquisition of various dimensions of knowledge (Godwin-Jones, 2011). Wong & Looi (2010) refer to it as a personal 'learning hub' because it serves as a readily accessible device. Due to the maintenance and development of relationships, as well as the ease and speed of access, a growing number of educators and learners are utilizing mobile phones for language learning (Thornton & Houser, 2005). It is asserted that mobile technologies offer numerous benefits for language learners, including flexibility, affordability, compactness, and ease of use (Yang, 2013). Consequently, in recent years, the mobile device has supplanted laptops or tablets for the purpose of language learning (Thornton & Houser, 2005). Currently, students are utilizing mobile phones for a variety of educational purposes. They investigate the significance of newly coined English terms (Reinders & Pegrum, 2016). In addition, they check for proper sentence mechanics and precise grammatical rules on Google rather than examining hardcopy manuscripts (Gafni et al., 2017). For newly enrolled

undergraduate students, who are in need of learning English language, appropriate knowledge of grammar is essential. Hence, they address the issues related to the wrong ordering of parts of speech within sentence structures using smartphones (Böhm & Constantine, 2016). The effective application of identical words functioning as various parts of speech is supported by learners utilizing different applications of mobile phones (Reinders & Pegrum, 2016). The screening process also includes verification of correct pronunciation (Berns et al., 2015). They listen to the correct pronunciation of the English terms they don't understand (Böhm & Constantine, 2016).

Mobile phones have become an increasingly invaluable tool for assisting learners with their homework (Kukulska-Hulme & Viberg, 2017). Mobile cameras can effectively capture images of work displayed on the board and record videos related to learning, which students can conveniently share via sharing option in the smartphones (He & Li, 2023). Students also utilize smart mobile applications for spelling checks (LeNoue et al., 2011). Moreover, voice recording serves as an effective tool for gathering audio evidence or obtaining peer feedback on language tasks (Menaka & Sankar, 2019). Aside from this, learners can use mobile devices as word play friends and digital storytelling tools (Niño, 2015). Additionally, forming a mobile group, engaging in phone blogging, utilizing Google SMS or Chacha, employing a Study Boost for review, and creating SMS-based chat rooms are various methods for making use of mobile phones in language learning process (Narváez et al., 2020). Real-time communication and engagement are fostered in the target language through interactive experiences and the understanding and creation of contemporary content on mobile devices (Kukulska-Hulme & Viberg, 2017). Besides, mobile devices serve as effective tools for enhancing skills in English, including listening, speaking, vocabulary, pronunciation, reading, grammar, and writing (Niño, 2015). This allows students to enhance their communication and language abilities (Narváez et al., 2020). Thus, the use of mobile phones emerges as an integral component of the language acquisition process. Therefore, it can be concluded that the incorporation of smartphones in language learning significantly improves students' foreign language learning opportunities by enabling social communication, internet access, and promoting motivation and creativity. The literature indicates that mobile phones have emerged as significant instruments for English education, providing various advantages for students, educators, and parents. The researchers of this study, however, believe that there are not enough studies on this specific topic. Furthermore, there appears to be a significant lack of studies regarding the use of specific mobile applications for language learning within the undergraduate education in Bangladesh context. Consequently, the research adds value to the domain of English education at this specific level.

Methodology

A questionnaire survey was conducted to explore learners' perceptions regarding the impact of mobile applications on their English vocabulary, grammar, reading, and writing skills. The questionnaire comprised 10 statements formulated in alignment with the study's objectives. Through simple random sampling, a total of 70 participants were selected from 7 colleges in Dhaka city that are affiliated with the University of Dhaka. Additionally, to assess the language proficiency of the participants, a preliminary English language test was conducted. The test was developed in alignment with the fundamental syllabus of the English language for undergraduate students across the seven colleges associated with the University of Dhaka. The assessment comprised various language components, including a reading comprehension section accompanied by short question answers (SQA), exercises on synonyms and antonyms, changes of parts of speech, and the task of writing a brief paragraph. Through the written portions, the researchers evaluated the students' vocabulary and grammatical knowledge in addition to their reading and writing abilities. The participants received training and guidance on utilizing two mobile applications, Duolingo and Babel, to enhance their language skills. The research team established a Facebook group for the participants to oversee and facilitate follow-up language activities, ensuring the effective and consistent use of the applications for language learning purposes. Following a month of engagement

with the mobile application, a post-test was conducted with the same participants who took part in the pre-test. The post-test featured the same language items as the pre-test question paper, maintaining a similar distribution of marks. After the data collection phase, a statistical analysis was conducted employing various mathematical or computational methods. The analysis of the data involved the application of both descriptive statistical techniques, such as frequency counts, mean, mode, and standard deviation, as well as inferential statistical methods, including regression analysis and correlation analysis.

Findings

The study began with a questionnaire survey aimed at investigating participants' perceptions regarding the impact of mobile applications on learning English vocabulary, grammar, and writing. Subsequently, a Pre-test was administered to assess the participants' English competency level, followed by a Post-test after the participants had engaged with the mobile application for language learning. A variety of statistical techniques were employed to analyze the data, and the findings from this analysis are discussed below:

Chart 1. Smartphones develop critical thinking

Chart 2. Smartphones for learning vocabulary

The first statement claimed that the use of smartphone develops the EFL learners' skill of critical thinking while learning English. The bar chart shows that about 71% of the respondents supported the claim. On the other hand, only about 14% of the respondents disagreed with the statement. The second statement was about the use of smartphone to promote learning EFL vocabulary. In response to this statement about 66% of the participants showed positive attitude. However, in this case, it is interesting that about 23% of the respondents chose 'Neutral' option from the scale.

Chart 3. Smartphones develop reading skills

Chart 4. Smartphones develop writing skills

According to the third claim, the use of smartphone promotes learning EFL reading comprehension. According to the bar chart, roughly 41% of respondents agreed with the assertion. However, about 37% of those surveyed said they disagreed with the statement. "The use of smartphone promotes learning EFL writing skills" was the claim in the fourth assertion. Approximately 51% of the participants responded positively to this statement. It's noteworthy to mention, though, that roughly 31% respondents selected the "Neutral" option on the scale.

Chart 5. Smartphones develop grammar skills

Chart 6. Smartphones for pair activities

The fifth statement claimed that the use of a smartphone is useful for me to learn EFL grammar items. The bar chart shows that about 69% of the respondents supported the claim. On the other hand, only about 11% of the respondents disagreed with the statement. However, it is interesting that 20% of the respondents selected the option “Neutral” from the scale. The sixth statement was about the use of smartphone to engage in pair activities while learning English. In response to this statement about 40% of the participants showed positive attitude. However, in this case, it is also interesting that about 26% of the respondents chose ‘Neutral’ option from the scale. Besides, 34% of the respondents disagreed with the statement.

Chart 7. Smartphones for group activities

Chart 8. Smartphones to communicate teachers

According to the seventh claim, the use of smartphone helps the learners actively engage in group activities while learning English. According to the bar chart, roughly 37% of respondents agreed with the assertion. However, about 29% of those surveyed said they disagreed with the statement. However, it is interesting that about 34% of the respondents selected the option “Neutral” from the scale. The use of smartphone helps the learners interact with their teachers while learning English was the claim covered by the eighth assertion. Approximately, 74% of the participants responded positively to this statement. It's noteworthy to mention, though, that roughly 26% respondents selected the "Neutral" option on the scale.

Chart 9. Smartphones to communicate with peers

Chart 10. Smartphones develop creativity

The use of smartphone helps the learners interact with their peers while learning English was the claim covered by the ninth assertion. Approximately 74% of the participants responded positively to this statement. It's noteworthy to mention, though, that roughly 26% respondents selected the "Neutral" option on the scale. The tenth statement claimed that the use of smartphone while learning English develops the EFL learners' skill of creativity. The bar chart shows that about 54% of the respondents supported the claim. On the other hand, only about 14% of the respondents disagreed with the statement. However, about 31% of the respondents chose "Neutral" option from the scale while giving their reaction to this statement.

Descriptive Statistics for Likert-Scale

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for Likert-scale Perceptions of Smartphone Use in EFL Learning

Variables	n	Mean	SD	Median	Trimmed	Min.	Max.	Skew.	Kurtosis	SE
The use of smartphone develops my skills of critical thinking while learning English	70	4.171	1.142	5	4.339	2	5	-0.908	-0.806	0.136
The use of smartphones promotes learning EFL vocabulary.	70	3.886	1.015	4	3.982	2	5	-0.431	-1.008	0.121
The use of smartphones promotes learning EFL reading comprehension	70	3.143	1.386	3	3.179	1	5	-0.059	-1.313	0.166
The use of smartphone promotes learning EFL writing skills	70	3.400	1.027	4	3.446	1	5	-0.525	-0.176	0.123
Use of a smartphone is useful for me to learn EFL grammar items.	70	3.829	1.035	4	3.946	1	5	-0.742	-0.022	0.124
Using smartphone, I can actively engage in pair activities while learning English	70	3.057	1.202	3	3.071	1	5	-0.108	-0.998	0.144
Using smartphone, I can actively engage in group activities while learning English	70	3.114	1.123	3	3.125	1	5	-0.100	-0.725	0.134
Using smartphone, I can easily interact with my teachers while learning English.	70	4.143	0.804	4	4.179	3	5	-0.256	-1.431	0.096
Using smartphone, I can easily interact with my peers while learning English.	70	4.029	0.742	4	4.036	3	5	-0.044	-1.207	0.089
The use of smartphone develops my skills of creativity while learning English	70	3.600	0.969	4	3.625	2	5	-0.090	-1.011	0.116

SD = Standard Deviation; Trimmed = Trimmed Mean; Min = Minimum; Max = Maximum; Skew = Skewness; SE = Standard Error

Table 1 provides descriptive statistics for perceptions of smartphone use in EFL learning. Results indicate that smartphone use is perceived as particularly effective for developing critical thinking (Mean = 4.17, SD = 1.14) and teacher interaction (Mean = 4.14, SD = 0.80), with relatively high median and trimmed mean values reflecting consistent responses. The skewness values are negative for most variables, indicating a tendency toward higher scores. Conversely, areas like group activities (Mean = 3.11, SD = 1.12) and pair activities (Mean = 3.06, SD = 1.20) show slightly lower mean scores, suggesting improvement opportunities in collaborative engagement using smartphones.

Descriptive Statistics for Pre-test and Post-test

Table 2. Pre-test and Post-test Descriptive Statistics for EFL Skills

Variables	n	Mean	SD	Median	Trimmed	Min.	Max.	Skew.	Kurtosis	SE	Variables
Pre											
Vocabulary	70	2.486	1.113	2	2.411	0	5	5	0.587	0.013	0.133
Grammar	70	1.371	0.736	1	1.321	0	5	5	1.841	6.769	0.088
SQA	70	4.336	1.835	4	4.348	1	8	7	0.039	-0.654	0.219
Writing	70	1.907	0.906	2	1.946	0	4	4	-0.202	-0.092	0.108
Total	70	10.093	2.810	10	10.063	2	17	15	0.081	0.500	0.336
Post											
Vocabulary	70	2.786	1.102	3	2.777	1	5	4	0.102	-0.733	0.132
Grammar	70	1.821	0.794	2	1.705	1	5	4	1.421	2.940	0.095
SQA	70	4.593	1.634	4.25	4.580	1	8	7	0.102	-0.465	0.195
Writing	70	1.950	0.905	2	1.973	0	4	4	-0.142	0.185	0.108
Total	70	11.179	2.918	11	11.223	3	17	14	-0.215	0.158	0.349

SD = Standard Deviation; Trimmed = Trimmed Mean; Min = Minimum; Max = Maximum; Skew = Skewness; SE = Standard Error; SQA = Speaking Quality & Accuracy

Table 2 highlights a comparison of pre- and post-test results for EFL skills. All skills demonstrate improvements post-intervention, with increases in vocabulary (Pre: Mean = 2.49, SD = 1.11; Post: Mean = 2.79, SD = 1.10) and grammar (Pre: Mean = 1.37, SD = 0.73; Post: Mean = 1.82, SD = 0.79) being particularly notable. Total scores also reflect an overall gain (Pre: Mean = 10.09, SD = 2.81; Post: Mean = 11.18, SD = 2.92). The skewness values suggest slight asymmetry in score distribution but remain within an acceptable range. These findings indicate that smartphone use positively impacts EFL learning outcomes, particularly in vocabulary and grammar mastery.

Paired Sample t-Test Results

Table 3. Paired t-Test Results Comparing Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores

Variable	Mean Difference	t-Value	df	p-Value	95% Confidence Interval
Vocabulary	-0.30	-3.59	69	0.001	[-0.467, -0.133]
Grammar	-0.45	-5.28	69	<0.001	[-0.620, -0.280]
SQA	-0.26	-1.92	69	0.059	[-0.524, 0.010]
Writing	-0.04	-0.42	69	0.675	[-0.246, 0.160]
Total Score	-1.09	-3.86	69	<0.001	[-1.646, -0.525]

df = Degrees of Freedom; *SQA* = Speaking Quality & Accuracy

The paired t-test results (Table 3) reveal significant improvements in EFL learning outcomes for several areas. Vocabulary showed a statistically significant mean difference of -0.30 ($p = 0.0006$), and grammar demonstrated a notable improvement with a mean difference of -0.45 ($p < 0.0001$). These results suggest that smartphone use had a meaningful impact on learning these skills. Similarly, the total score exhibited a significant increase (mean difference = -1.09, $p = 0.0002$), underscoring the overall effectiveness of smartphone use in enhancing EFL performance. However, speaking quality and accuracy (SQA) and writing did not show statistically significant changes. While SQA approached significance ($p = 0.0586$, mean difference = -0.26), writing displayed no meaningful improvement ($p = 0.6745$, mean difference = -0.04). These findings indicate that while smartphones are effective for certain aspects of EFL learning, their impact may vary across different skills.

Correlation Matrix of the Perceptions in EFL Learning and Smartphone Use

The correlation matrix (Figure 1 below) highlights relationships among different perceptions of smartphone use (Q1 to Q10) in EFL learning. High correlations are observed between Q1 ("Critical Thinking") and Q5 ("Grammar Learning") ($r = 0.88$), as well as between Q2 ("Vocabulary Learning") and Q3 ("Reading Comprehension") ($r = 0.92$). This indicates that students who perceive smartphones as fostering critical thinking and grammar skills tend to view them as similarly beneficial for vocabulary and reading comprehension. Lower correlations are seen between Q10 ("Creativity") and most other variables, such as Q1 ($r = 0.19$) and Q2 ($r = 0.31$), suggesting a weaker perceived association between creativity and other EFL skills facilitated by smartphones. Additionally, moderate correlations between Q6 ("Pair Activities") and Q7 ("Group Activities") ($r = 0.79$) highlight the potential of smartphones for collaborative learning.

Below in Figure 1, Q1 = The use of smartphone develops my skills of critical thinking while learning English; Q2 = The use of smartphone promotes learning EFL vocabulary; Q3 = The use of smartphone promotes learning EFL reading comprehension; Q4 = The use of smartphone promotes learning EFL writing skills; Q5 = Use of a smartphone is useful for me to learn EFL grammar items; Q6 = Using smartphone, I can actively engage in pair activities while learning English; Q7 = Using smartphone, I can actively engage in group activities while learning English; Q8 = Using smartphone, I can easily interact with my teachers while learning English; Q9 = Using smartphone, I can easily interact with my peers while learning English; Q10 = The use of smartphone develops my skills of creativity while learning English

Figure 1. Correlation Matrix of Smartphone Use Perceptions in EFL Learning

Correlation Coefficient of Pre-Test vs. Post-Test Scores

Figure 2. Scatter Plot of Pre-Test vs. Post-Test Scores with Correlation Coefficient

Figure 2 presents a scatter plot illustrating the relationship between pre-test and post-test scores for EFL learning, with a correlation coefficient ($r = 0.664$) prominently displayed. The moderate positive correlation indicates that students with higher pre-test scores tend to achieve higher post-test scores. This relationship is visually reinforced by the linear regression line, which trends upward, suggesting consistent improvement across the dataset.

95% Confidence Intervals for Improvements in Each EFL Skill

Figure 3. Violin Plot for Improvements in Each EFL Skill with 95% Confidence Intervals

The violin plot (Figure 3) displays the distribution of pre-test and post-test scores across EFL skills, highlighting notable improvements in Vocabulary and Grammar, as shown by higher median scores and less overlap between pre- and post-test confidence intervals. For SQA and Writing, the overlap indicates smaller or more variable progress. Post-test scores are generally more concentrated toward higher values, especially for Grammar and Vocabulary, underscoring the significant impact of smartphone use in these areas.

Discussion

This study primarily examined the influence of smartphone usage on the development of grammar and vocabulary skills in undergraduate EFL learners. The researchers directed the students to specific use of two mobile applications for the acquisition of English vocabulary and grammar. The study establishes that undergraduates can achieve improved exposure to the English language through smartphone usage. Nonetheless, the study indicates that challenges persist in the utilization of smartphones within the context of EFL learning in Bangladesh, particularly regarding the development of English writing skills. Studies indicate that Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) has notably influenced language acquisition, presenting both advantages and obstacles (Burston, 2014a, Burston, 2014b). Smartphones enhance accessibility, enabling learners to practice at any time and in any location, thereby overcoming the limitations of time and space. Consequently, smartphones serve as valuable tools for formal education and self-directed learning (Çakmak, 2019). Applications and platforms provide adaptive learning pathways tailored to user performance, allowing learners to select specific skills to concentrate on, such as vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation (Godwin-Jones, 2011). This study's findings also support that MALL serves as a significant enhancement to traditional language learning for adult English language learners in

contexts such as Bangladesh. When integrated thoughtfully, it fosters engagement, autonomy, and consistent practice; however, optimal results are achieved when used in conjunction with other methods, particularly for enhancing fluency and deeper linguistic skills.

The study's findings further indicate that mobile applications can significantly contribute to learners' development of EFL grammar. Many other Researches confirm that utilizing Duolingo for English grammar acquisition can be effective, as it employs gamification techniques that render grammar learning engaging (Chen et al., 2019). With Duolingo, learners of various skill levels can begin with basic grammatical principles, such as sentence construction, and work their way up to verb tenses, prepositions, and other topics (Osawaru & Unachukwu, 2024). This language learning application integrates grammar within meaningful sentences, enabling learners to observe the application of rules in authentic conversation (Narváez et al., 2020). Conversely, according to many researchers, Babbel is a well-known language-learning application that demonstrates strengths in teaching English grammar, an area where Duolingo is less emphasized (Osawaru & Unachukwu, 2024). Babbel incorporates explicit instruction of grammar rules in its lessons. Students frequently encounter explicit elucidations of tenses, sentence structure, articles, and additional grammatical elements (Samin et al., 2023). The researchers of this study believe that learners can engage with grammar in context, and Babbel provides explanations for the usage of specific forms, enhancing comprehension. Moreover, the study has also found that smartphones significantly impact the development of vocabulary skills in EFL students. Research indicates that Duolingo is effective for enhancing English vocabulary, as it is structured to facilitate the natural absorption of new words through repetition and contextual learning. Conversely, Babbel is effective for acquiring English vocabulary, particularly for learners who favor structured lessons and real-world context rather than gamified repetition. Hence it can be said that the use of mobile applications for learning English grammar and vocabulary has gained significant popularity for valid reasons. These applications provide a flexible, engaging, and effective method for enhancing language skills while mobile.

Conclusion

The findings indicate that both educators and learners recognize the importance of mobile apps in enhancing the EFL learning process. The undergraduate level learners in Bangladesh can actively engage with smartphones to enhance their exposure to genuine language learning experiences. They can extensively utilize mobile phones to enhance their EFL grammar and vocabulary skills. Several significant discoveries reveal that EFL educators and learners possess access to Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL), which they utilize in the process of teaching and learning English. MALL serves as a significant enhancement to conventional language learning methods, particularly benefiting those at the beginner and intermediate levels. When integrated thoughtfully, it fosters engagement, autonomy, and consistent practice; however, for optimal outcomes, it should be utilized in conjunction with other approaches, particularly for enhancing fluency and deeper linguistic competencies. Future studies could investigate tailored strategies to improve less responsive areas such as writing and speaking quality.

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